

TECHNOLOGIES RELATED TO WELDING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7370114>

Introduction. Welding is a manufacturing process that joins materials, usually metals or thermoplastics, using high heat to melt the parts and allow them to cool. Welding differs from low-temperature methods such as soldering and brazing in that they do not melt the base metal (parent metal).

In addition to melting the base metal, a filler is usually added to the joint to form a pool of molten material (weld pool) to form a joint based on the configuration of the weld (bored, full penetration, fillet, etc.) cools, may be stronger than the base material. Pressure can also be used in conjunction with heat or by itself to weld. Welding also requires some form of shielding to protect filler metals or molten metals from contamination or oxidation.

Main part. A variety of energy sources can be used for welding, including gas flame (chemical), electric arc (electric), laser, electron beam, friction, and ultrasound. Although mostly an industrial process, welding can be performed in a variety of environments, including outdoors, underwater, and in space. Welding is a hazardous job and precautions must be taken to avoid burns, electric shock, vision impairment, inhalation of toxic gases and fumes, and exposure to strong UV radiation.

Gas welding

The most common gas welding process is oxy-fuel welding, also known as oxyacetylene welding. It is one of the oldest and most versatile welding processes, but in recent years it has become less popular in industrial applications. It is still widely used in the welding of pipes and tubes, as well as in repair work.

The equipment is relatively inexpensive and simple, and typically uses the combustion of acetylene in oxygen to produce a welding flame of about 3100 °C (5600 °F). Because the flame is less concentrated than an electric arc, it causes the weld to cool more slowly, which can lead to more residual stresses and weld failure, but it makes it easier to weld high-alloy steels. A similar process, commonly called oxygen cutting, is used to cut metals.

Arc welding

These processes use a welding power source to create and maintain an electric arc between the electrode and the base material to melt the metals at the weld point. They can use direct current (DC) or alternating current (AC) and

consumable or non-consumable electrodes. The weld area is sometimes protected by a type of inert or semi-inert gas known as a shielding gas, and sometimes a filler is also used.

Figure-1. Diagram of arc and weld area, in shielded metal arc welding.

1. Coating Flow
2. Rod
3. Shield Gas
4. Fusion
5. Base metal
6. Weld metal
7. Solidified Slag

Resistance welding

Resistance welding involves the generation of heat by passing current through the resistance caused by contact between two or more metal surfaces. When a high current (1000-100,000 A) passes through the metal, small pools of molten metal are formed at the welding site. In general, resistance welding methods are efficient and cause little pollution, but their application is somewhat limited and the cost of the equipment can be high.

Conclusion. Until the end of the 19th century, the only welding process was forge welding, which blacksmiths had used for millennia to join iron and steel by heating and hammering. Arc welding and oxy-fuel welding were among the first processes to develop late in the century, and electric resistance welding

followed soon after. Welding technology advanced quickly during the early 20th century as world wars drove the demand for reliable and inexpensive joining methods. Following the wars, several modern welding techniques were developed, including manual methods like shielded metal arc welding, now one of the most popular welding methods, as well as semi-automatic and automatic processes such as gas metal arc welding, submerged arc welding, flux-cored arc welding and electroslag welding. Developments continued with the invention of laser beam welding, electron beam welding, magnetic pulse welding, and friction stir welding in the latter half of the century. Today, as the science continues to advance, robot welding is commonplace in industrial settings, and researchers continue to develop new welding methods and gain greater understanding of weld quality.

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